

REGINE CRESPIN

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Septembre 22nd - 2000

Dear John,

First of all, very
Happy Birthday to you !!
And welcome to the Club !!

I love you very much
and I want, once more, to tell
you how much I have enjoyed
our long collaboration, not
only in music but in
laughters and friendship -